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Safety and Security: A 21st Century Philippine Public School Quagmire

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To foster a secure and conducive learning environment, a safety and security procedure must be in place to ensure the well-being of students, faculty, and staff. The ever-evolving landscape of protecting lives and property needs a robust safety and security plan. This document should represent the collective efforts of the school community to create a resilient and responsive system that adheres to national guidelines and considers the unique characteristics and challenges of a school community. It should encompass various scenarios, ranging from natural disasters to potential safety and security threats, providing a roadmap of coordination into an adequate response.

Arguments can no longer be raised as to the safety and security of students in a school. However, an analysis of implementation or actual situation from the ground, at a school level, would yield a rife anecdote worthy of collaborative re-examination.

A working theory is drawn from a Latin phrase *in loco parentis*, enshrined in Article 218 of the Family Code, enabling the unique authority of the school, its administrators and teachers, or the individual or institution engaged in child care shall have outstanding parental control and responsibility over the minor while under their supervision or custody.

This authority and responsibility shall apply to all authorized activities, whether inside or outside the school's premises, entity, or institution. This blanket rule is void of specifics subsumed to cover the central thesis for reconsideration. The first two terms have been tested and evolved with modern times, as should be expected since the 21st century began twenty-two years ago. Safety in the workplace refers to procedures or any means, policies, or control of specific internal work-related hazards. On the other hand, an organization's main security thrust is to protect its most valuable asset, its people.

Regrettably, teachers get the blame for it is convenient to attribute negligence to all injuries that students may receive, even if it is self-inflicted. Mud had been thrown at them as a natural response from the aggrieved, but once the truth came out, no one rescued them to revive their shattered dignity. While it is true that people are the organization's most valuable

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asset, they are also the greatest threat to the safety and security of the workplace. Their attitudes and behavior can easily break down a well-planned protection of employees. Such teachers' attitudes are prevalent in Philippine public schools due to safety and security are not part of operational expenses.

It is good that most schools in **the National Capital Region (NCR)** have their **Local Government Unit (LGU)** as a stakeholder. They allocate additional funds for schools under their jurisdiction. They provide additional funds to third-party security personnel and job orders (**JOs**) for utilities/janitorial services. However, reinforcement from the LGU needs to be more well-trained if they are at all. Most of these Job Orders are political appointees. It is like adding salt to an already open wound. The loyalty of these people is not for the service they should provide to the school as supplemental security and utility personnel but instead to their political patron, making them an additional threat to the school.

Contrast this situation in provincial schools where all-around utilities act as security personnel. They do so due to the incomparable obedience of students and teaching personnel in the countryside. However, it is reprehensible as far as safety and security are concerned, and must not be dependent on the school principal because they are routinely moved every two to three years. It is a rare tenure to stay in one school for five years or more.

Given these difficulties, here are some suggested room for improvement in Safety and Security in public schools:

1. The school head or authorized representative must have complete administrative control over all personnel (inclusive from LGU) tasked to implement safety and security in emergencies.
2. A systematic structure or flow chart where authority emanates and is carried out must be laid, disseminated, and understood by the school community.
3. Administrative sanctions from light to heavy must be spelled out in case the offense is committed in times of emergency. An equivalent must be applied to third-party service providers and job order personnel.
4. Regular training is necessary to develop a conscious habit of safety and security prevention.
5. Constant funding is necessary for sustainable training.
6. Security infrastructure is essential to enhance safety measures.
7. Make or adapt safety and security protocols suitable for individual school contexts.

Add to the concern is the conduct of the **Disaster, Risk, Reduction, and Management (DRRM)** exercise, but, again, it employs teachers to shepherd their students out of school to comply with standard time in emergency exits. Thus, integrating these three (DRRM, Safety, and Security) was recently put forward as a primer guide.

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Given these circumstances or threats, an emergency structure must be created to handle the complex merging of DRRM, Safety, and Security needs. The delegation of a crisis manager is critical to handling the flow of communication, easing decision-making needs, and assessing damage control to contain emergencies. The goal is to achieve Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude (KSA).

Regular training would reinforce the needed response to any emergency, whether announced or unannounced, to ensure a safe and secure workplace/learning environment. A feedback mechanism must also be in place to continuously improve procedures and appropriate responses, as the case may be.

Whatever form, substance, or standard operating procedure, there must be an articulated contingency plan for all schools to follow or improve upon to suit individual/contextual school needs. An administrative or criminal liability must be included to make sure teaching and non-teaching personnel feel that safety and security are serious and everyone's business.

The writer is a principal author of the Cluster Approved Institutionalized Safety and Security Integrated-Contingency Plan (ISSIP-CP).

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